

NDAC/LO/016

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Definition of mean abscissa

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Problem

The set solution simulations performed at the Geodetic Institute assume that a star (number i) has a unique position in the set (j), i.e. u_{ij} , ρ_{ij} = independent of time (or frame number, k). The set solution provides the least-squares estimate of u_{ij} , subject to a number of constraints (fixed ρ_{ij} , attitude components about $\underline{x}$ and $\underline{y}$, and abscissa for an origin star).

In the actual reductions, the stellar position changes even from one frame to the next, due to aberration, proper motion, parallax, and gravitational light deflexion by the earth and sun. Thus we should write (u_{ijk}, ρ_{ijk}) for the instantaneous position (at frame mid-time t_k).

Of course we cannot solve for a changing quantity (u_{ijk}). But if the variations are either exactly known (as is almost the case for aberration and light deflexion), or linear with time (as for proper motion and parallax in a 12 hour interval), one can define a mean position in the set, the abscissa of which may be solved. Because of the unknown, but linear, variation due to proper motion and parallax, the mean position must be referred to the mean time of observation in the set.

This note is concerned with the precise definition of the mean position, and how the set observation equation should be formulated in terms of the new variables.

Proposed definition

The successive steps for computing the proper direction ($\underline{u}$) to a star, given its astrometric parameters, is schematically shown in Figure 1. Unless we introduce (quite artificially) sub-levels in this diagram, such as the geocentric proper direction, it is evident that the only feasible definition of mean position is the satellitocentric coordinate direction ($\bar{\underline{u}}$) at the mean time of observation. Referring to star i in set j we use the notation $\bar{\underline{u}}_{ij}$ for

FIGURE 1. Transformations leading from the barycentric position at TEPOCH, (α_0, δ_0) to the proper direction seen by the moving observer. Cf (A.2.1) to (A.2.9). ρ_0, ρ_S, ρ_E = satellitocentric coordinates of the barycentre, the sun, and the earth; $\underline{\hat{v}}$ = velocity of satellite in the natural frame.

the mean position; the corresponding mean time of observation is $\bar{\bar{t}}_{ij}$. It is seen that $\bar{\underline{u}}$ is the lowest level in the diagram at which all the astrometric parameters are incorporated; it is also the highest level at which the variations over a 12 hour interval can be regarded as linear with time. (Both the diurnal aberration and the deflexion by the earth are significantly non-linear.)

With $\underline{\tilde{R}}_j = (x_{Rj} \ y_{Rj} \ z_{Rj})$ being the reference system of the set [given in equatorial coordinates as $\underline{\tilde{E}}'_j$, see (A.11.1)], we thus define the mean abscissa $\bar{\underline{u}}_{ij}$ and the mean ordinate $\bar{\bar{\rho}}_{ij}$ by

$$\bar{\underline{u}}_{ij} = x_{Rj} \cos \bar{\bar{\rho}}_{ij} \cos \bar{\underline{u}}_{ij} + y_{Rj} \cos \bar{\bar{\rho}}_{ij} \sin \bar{\underline{u}}_{ij} + z_{Rj} \sin \bar{\bar{\rho}}_{ij} \quad (1)$$

or

$$\bar{\underline{u}}_{ij} = \text{ATAN2}(y'_{Rj} \bar{\underline{u}}_{ij}, z'_{Rj} \bar{\underline{u}}_{ij}) \quad (2)$$

$$\bar{\bar{\rho}}_{ij} = \arcsin z'_{Rj} \bar{\underline{u}}_{ij} \quad (3)$$

Here, $\bar{\underline{u}}_{ij}$ is computed with time argument

$$\bar{\bar{t}}_{ij} \approx \langle t_{ijk} \rangle_k \quad (4)$$

i.e. as the average of the frame mid-times at which the star was observed. This definition cannot be very strict since the observation weights may change in the course of the solution; hence $\bar{t}_{ij}$ must be defined at the beginning of the solution and then kept constant even if some observations are later discarded.

The observation equation

The set solution should estimate the following unknowns:

- $\bar{U}_{ij}$ = mean abscissa of star i
 ψ_{jk} = attitude correction about z in frame k ($= \overline{\Delta\omega}$ in NDAC/LO/001)
 $\underline{d}_j$ = a vector of field distortion parameters

In principle, the solution minimises the norm of the weighted noise vector in

$$G_{\text{cat}}(\bar{U}_{ij}, \psi_{jk}, \underline{d}_j) + \text{noise} = G_{\text{obs},ijk} + \text{integer} \quad (5)$$

where the function G_{cat} also depends on a number of additional parameters, which however are not updated by the solution. The conventional observation equation, (001.1), is a linearisation of (5) around its m :th approximation,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial G_{\text{cat}}}{\partial \bar{U}_{ij}} \Delta \bar{U}_{ij}^{(m)} + \frac{\partial G_{\text{cat}}}{\partial \psi_{jk}} \Delta \psi_{jk}^{(m)} + \frac{\partial G_{\text{cat}}}{\partial \underline{d}_j} \Delta \underline{d}_j^{(m)} + \text{noise} = \\ = G_{\text{obs},ijk} - G_{\text{cat}}(\bar{U}_{ij}^{(m)}, \psi_{jk}^{(m)}, \underline{d}_j^{(m)}) + \text{integer} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

leading to the updates

$$\bar{U}_{ij}^{(m+1)} = \bar{U}_{ij}^{(m)} + \Delta \bar{U}_{ij}^{(m)} \quad (7)$$

etc. Expressions for the partial derivatives in (6) are found in NDAC/LO/001. Here we shall concentrate on the evaluation of G_{cat} , which is not at all trivial. In fact, a rigorous precept does not exist, due to the (at this stage) unknown proper motion and parallax effects. However, the following scheme should be close enough to a rigorous evaluation.

1. Given the mean position, $(\bar{u}_{ij}, \bar{\rho}_{ij})$ at $\bar{t}_{ij}$, compute $\bar{u}_{ij}$ from (1).

2. Apply a priori proper motion and parallax variation if required, according to the approximate formula

$$\bar{u}_{ijk} = \bar{u}_{ij} + (t_k - \bar{t}_{ij}) \left[\dot{u}_o + (\mathbb{I} - \bar{u}_{ij} \bar{u}_{ij}') \dot{\rho}_o \Pi \right] \quad (8)$$

The variation may exceed 0.1 mas in 6 hours if $|\dot{u}_o| > 2 \cdot 10^{-14}$ rad/s ≈ 0.1 as/yr or $\Pi > 0.02$ as. $\dot{u}_o$ and Π are taken from the current (or input) catalogue.

3. Apply gravitational deflexion and aberration according to (A.2.7) - (A.2.9); the result is the proper direction u_{ijk} .

4. Using the attitude angles α_{zk} , δ_{zk} , ω_k , compute the field coordinates f_{ijk} , η_{ijk} , ζ_{ijk} .

5. Subtract ψ_k from the longitudinal field coordinate η_{ijk} .

6. Apply d_j to f_{ijk} , η_{ijk} , ζ_{ijk} according to (001.12) in order to get $G_{cat,ijk}$.

The above scheme replaces the one described in NDAC/LO/001 for computing G_{cat} .